

PROTOTYPE OF OPEN HYDROPONICS TOOLS AND SYSTEMS AND PROTOCOL FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION

D5.4

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Short Description
<p>This documentation forms the basis for the realization, implementation and management of the project prototype(s) of simplified hydroponics and community garden. This version includes the case study realized in the Tunisia Food Hub (Jundouba) and in the Ethiopian one (Akaki / Nifas Silk). It includes the prototype objectives, general considerations and recommendations together with the following two sections:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the prototype section that provides a scientific-technological description of the R&I process carried out to realize the prototype (final innovative method / system / tool / product) as result of the testing phase in lab / at small-scale level (WP4) and feedback gathered from the in-field validation (WP5). According to the impact pathway approach, it describes the conducted activities, the reached outputs and outcomes, and the obtained measures of relevant key performance indicators demonstrating the impact; - the protocol section that adopts an operational perspective to describe how to implement and manage the prototype, thus ensuring its full functionality and usability. It includes deployment requirements, procedures, methods, techniques, and practical considerations. Moreover, the protocols generate guidelines (D4.2), practice abstracts (D6.5) and training materials (D5.1).

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Abbreviations and glossary

Abbreviation/specialist term	Explanation
SHS	Simplified Hydroponic System
LUE	Land Use Efficiency
WUE	Water Use Efficiency
NUE	Nitrogen Use Efficiency
CBA	Cost Benefit Analysis
UHS	Upgraded Hydroponic System

1. Background

1.1 Prototype motivations and objectives

Problem(s) the (open) prototype aims to solve or the user needs it intends to address, concept, specific objectives and targets.

Food Hub Jendouba (TN)

Smallholder farmers from the rural area of Fernena, located in the Jendouba governorate of Northern Tunisia, are facing increasing challenges. Rising cultivation costs, primarily driven by the expenses for fertilizers, planting materials, and pesticides, are compounded by the growing threat of water scarcity. As a result, alternative farming solutions are urgently needed to enhance the resilience of local agricultural activities. Vegetables cultivation offers a promising opportunity for smallholder farmers in this region. Compared to traditional staple crops, such as barley and wheat, which are commonly grown for food and animal feed, vegetables have a higher added value and profitability. Moreover, vegetables are vital for human nutrition, with daily consumption of around 400 grams per person being recommended for a balanced and healthy diet. However, the hilly terrain of Fernena presents specific challenges, as the area suffers from water scarcity, salinization, and soil desertification—issues exacerbated by ongoing climate change. One promising solution is the adoption of closed-loop hydroponic systems. These systems, which either use alternative growing media (hydroponics on substrate) or eliminate soil entirely (with roots suspended in nutrient solutions), can significantly reduce water usage by recirculating water within the system. This innovative technique, though new to the region, could offer a sustainable farming alternative. Nevertheless, the development of low-cost hydroponic solutions is crucial to ensure they are accessible to smallholder farmers.

Additionally, community vegetables gardens are an alternative solution in Fernena, as they can provide social and economic benefits to local farmers. Farmers can share investment costs, facilitating technology adoption, and increasing the market value of their produce. The introduction of water-saving technologies, such as drip irrigation and mulching, further supports the sustainability of these gardens.

Furthermore, food processing (e.g., drying) can increase the economic value of the raw food produces by increasing their storability and offering innovative and diversified food products in local market. Another important available resource to local farmers is a solar dryer, established as part of a parallel task in the project.

This technology offers to farmers the possibility to process their produces through drying, increasing both the storability and market value. By expanding into food processing, such as drying, farmers can introduce diversified and innovative products to local markets, thereby boosting their economic returns.

Food Hub Akaki / Nifas Silk (ET)

Alarming urban growth is occurring worldwide. It is occurring in developing countries that are projected to account for 80% of world urban population by 2030 (UNEP, 2007; Ash et al., 2008). The Ethiopian average urban growth rate of 5% per annum is one of the fastest in the world (NUPI, 2003). Its urban population is concentrated in few cities, predominantly in Addis Ababa, the country's Capital City and regional cities such as Mekelle City in northern Ethiopia. The cities' built up area has gone beyond the prevailing infrastructure and basic urban services (Minwyelet, 2005; Yirgalem 2008).

Urbanization causes emigration of the young people from the countryside and rural areas in search of opportunities which in turn threatens the already strained situation of food and nutrition security in the developing countries. As urbanization grows at unprecedented scale and the natural environment becomes fragmented and fragile, the importance of urban green spaces is getting attention in requirement of mitigation measures for improving ecosystem services, urban quality life, health and wellbeing (de Groot et al., 2002; Tratalos et al., 2007; Tzoulas et al., 2007; Goddard, 2009). Moreover, achieving food security for the expanding urban population presupposes production of local food in the limited spaces and with the lowest possible use of municipal water (FAO, 2005). However, production systems at urban private gardens are highly heterogeneous in terms of size, form and function due to variations in management (Cameron et al., 2012).

Private urban garden in general refers to private spaces surrounding to dwellings, which may include lawns, ornamental and vegetable plots, ponds, paths, and temporary buildings such as sheds, either privately owned or rented (Smith et al., 2011; Cameron et al., 2012). A number of socio-economic, biophysical and policy-related factors affect private urban garden development. For instance, greater housing density is linked to smaller garden sizes, but not necessarily less urban green spaces (Smith et al., 2009). Socio-economic variables (e.g. population and housing density, education, home ownership) are also better predictors of the extent and the type of vegetation cover in private gardens (Luck et al., 2009). Larger private gardens are associated with higher income or educated residents and tend to have more vegetation and greater diversity of plants (Daniels and

Kirkpatrick, 2006). These all urges to have baseline information on the status and impact of private gardens and develop standard designs to satisfy requirements of the newly emerging urban and peri-urban green infrastructures that cherish better quality of life in urban and peri-urban areas.

In peri-urban areas, stunting is common related to a lack of micronutrients and vitamins in the diet of the population (FAO 2004a, 2009). Urbanization brings changes in food consumption behavior, purchasing habits and consumers' location. The constraints that likely rise with urban expansion are high food access costs, unstable food availability and deteriorating food quality and hygiene (Aragrande and Argenti, 2001). Vegetables play a fundamental role in the human nutrition as source of minerals, vitamins and other antioxidant compounds. Thus, increasing the cultivation and the use of vegetables has the potential to improve health condition and reduce poverty (Gianquinto et al., 2007).

Information and communication technologies permit an easy, immediate and up-to-date access to information on markets, and business opportunities while it is difficult to transfer technology to urban and peri-urban farmers. Thus, local governments should play a critical role in developing strategic partnerships with the private sector, NGOs and civil institutions.

Urban and peri-urban agriculture (UPA) is evolving fast, intensifying horticulture to secure year-round supply of fresh produce to consumers. Within this context, FAO has been supporting UPA programs focusing on vegetable production with due consideration for safe vegetable food product marketing, distribution and consumption. Thus, FAO appropriates “simplified” hydroponics (SH) gardening systems for improving the local supply of safe, fresh and nutritious food (Carrasco and Izquierdo, 1996).

Given the context, the main objectives are:

- Assess the existing private gardens, current status, and their relevance for quality urban life and sustainable development.
- Prepare alternative design of private gardens that integrates the various components (green, grey and blue components),
- Improve productivity and quality of private gardens through selection of appropriate plant species and development of appropriate simple hydroponics technologies suitable for urban precision farming systems
- Establish methods of conserving environmental resources (land and water) maintaining productive and healthy private gardens contributing to safe and nutritious green food supply to markets.

2. Prototype

This section provides a scientific-technological description of the R&I process carried out to realize the prototype (final new method / system / tool / product) as result of the testing phase in lab / at small-scale level (WP4) and feedback gathered from the field innovation validation (WP5).

According to the impact pathway approach (in line with D4.12 focused on WP4), it describes the conducted activities, the reached outputs and outcomes, and the measurement of relevant key performance indicators demonstrating the impact.

Food Hub	Food Product
Jendouba (TN)	Hydroponic systems (fresh vegetables and legumes)
Jendouba (TN)	Community gardens (fresh vegetables and legumes)
Akaki / Nifas Silk (ET)	Hydroponic peri-urban systems (green vegetables: lettuce, spinach and cauliflower)

2.1 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating

Brief description of the scientific-technological criteria and R&I path (development, test, and validation) for the realization of the innovative technology / system / process / tool.

Food Hub Jendouba (TN)

The project in the Jendouba Food Hub focused on developing two low-cost Simplified Hydroponic Systems (SHSs) aimed at optimizing water use and promoting circular economy practices. The first system, referred to as the “box system,” consisted of a wooden box elevated from the ground and irrigated through a gravity-fed drip irrigation system. The second SHS was a sloped garden where locally sourced plastic bottles were aligned in rows and filled with a growing substrate where plant were transplanted. A gravity-fed irrigation system delivered nutrients to the plants, with both systems incorporating drainage features that allowed for the recirculation of excess water back into the irrigation tank, making them closed-loop systems.

A comparative agronomic trial was conducted to evaluate the performance of both SHSs using romaine lettuce. Two different growing substrates were tested in the plastic bottle system: commercial perlite and a substrate made from locally produced charred wheat straw. Results showed that the plastic bottle SHS

outperformed the box system (which did not yield satisfactory results due to its poor drainage capacity), and the charred straw proved to be an effective alternative to commercial perlite in these simplified hydroponic settings. Following the trial, the systems were demonstrated to local farmers to gather their feedback, which led to the refinement and potential upgrading of the system during the validation phase.

In parallel, a community garden was established within the same Food Hub. This garden is designed to improve access to land and introduce farmers to innovative agricultural and food processing technologies while encouraging collaboration among local farmers. The garden can accommodate up to 56 farmers, each allocated a 100 m² plot. Each plot is equipped with a drip irrigation system, and eco-friendly agricultural techniques will be promoted through technical training provided by local extension services (CRDA). Farmers can choose to grow crops either for personal consumption or for sale in local markets. An analysis of local market demands was conducted by INAT (Institute National Agronomique de Tunisie) to determine the most demanded crops, which include tomatoes, garlic, onions, and strawberries. Additionally, farmers in the community garden have access to a solar dryer, installed by INAT within the Food Hub. This technology enables them to produce high-value products such as dried vegetables and powdered spices, which can help reduce food waste by improving storability and enhancing the marketability of their produce.

Food Hub Akaki / Nifas Silk (ET)

Location of the study area

Unproductive site (18m²) located in Mekelle city, Tigray Ethiopia (in the Illalla Bizuhan Mariam Nuns Monastery), was allotted to set it productive through the simple standing hydroponics system (SSHS) technology. Eucalyptus poles were used to provide support for the SSHS installation. The wooden support was constructed with a slightly north easterly slope of 2%.

Ten grey colored PVC tubes (each six meters long and 110 mm diameter) were purchased. Punches of holes (8 mm diameter and 15 cm apart of each other) were prepared on each of the PVCs resulting in 40 holes made ready to be planting (Fig 1). Planting plastic tea cups were also purchased each of which were torn narrowly at the bottom and lower sides to allow rooting of seedlings into the nutrient solution filled into each of the PVCs. The PVCs were filled in nutrient solution. The cups were filled with substrate of perlite mixed with coconut peats occupying only one-third of the cup volume.

Figure 1. Layout of the experiment on romaine lettuce in Mekelle city, Ethiopia: (a) soil less system using PVCs (110mm diameter and 6 m long, each having 40 planting holes) on eucalyptus wood support, and (b) soil system. The soilless system used 48% of the water used by the soil system under similar field conditions.

Romaine lettuce seedlings managed for one month in raised in seedling trays in the Mekelle Biotechnology Center were transplanted to each of the cups and then placed in each of the planting holes on the PVCs. The levelling of each of the PVCs was checked to have a balanced volume of the nutrient supply to all the lettuce plants throughout the growing period. The cumulative water supply was optimized at mean 27.7 liters per m² for the hydroponics (soilless) systems versus 63.3 liters per m² for the romaine lettuce planted on soils as control starting after transplanting period (Table 1).

Table 1. Measured water consumed (l/m²) for growing romaine lettuce in Mekelle simple hydroponics systems versus growing on soil

Planting lines	Transplanting stage (l)	Middle stage (l)	Developmental stage (l)	Maturity stage (l)	Spacing (m ² /plant)	Cumulative use (l/m ²)
Soilless	15	15	20	50	0.045	27.7
With soils	30	60	100	190	0.075	63.3

Determining leaf area index (LAI)

The leaf area of the lettuce leaf was measured overlaying a transparent sheet printed to a grid area of 1cm² on top of leaves of the sampled plant. The lower, middle and upper leaves of the sampled plant were measured. The LAI was determined by dividing the total leaf area to the ground area occupied by the hydroponics system. The ground area was calculated by calculating the total cross-sectional area of the PVCs (110mm diameter and 6 m long) and multiplied by the number of the PVCs installed in the system.

Determining growth and biomass

The electrical conductivity was monitored to keep the proper soluble solution concentration within the acceptable range (i.e., 1.5 to 2.5 dS/m) throughout the growing period. The total biomass was measured by taking the whole plant from its whole adjusted to the cup and its substrate that have no plants. The above ground biomass was measured at maturity during harvesting of the lettuce. The marketable biomass was measured after removal the older leaves from the plant based on local practices and preferences of consumers in the local market.

Measuring chlorophyll and estimating nitrogen content

The chlorophyll meter (MC 100) was used to measure the chlorophyll content of lower, middle and upper leaves of the sampled plant during different growth periods. The nitrogen content of the leaves was estimated from the readings of the chlorophyll meter by fitting in non-linear regression model of the type

$$y = ax^2 + bx + c$$

where a and b are parameters determined in the regression.

All necessary data on amount of water and nutrient solution applied, and plant parameters were collected on the various growth stages. Descriptive statistics and analysis of variance was carried out excel and minitab software version 19 (Barbara, et al 1972).

2.2 Summary of the outputs

2.2.1 Results and achievements

Short description of the new technologies / systems / processes / tools / food products.

Food Hub Jendouba (TN)

The agronomic trial revealed that the plastic bottle-based SHS performed better than the raised box system. In the raised box system, lettuce growth was unsatisfactory due to poor drainage. Conducted during the winter, the substrate—a mix of local soil and cow manure—failed to drain rainfall adequately, leading to waterlogging. Conversely, the plastic bottle system excelled, and the locally produced charred straw substrate performed comparably to commercial perlite (although with some drawbacks related with excessive water retention), making it a viable, cost-effective alternative for hydroponic cultivation (Cerasola et al., 2024, in press).

Following validation with local farmers, several system upgrades were deemed necessary. These included physical protection from insects, automated irrigation, and the addition of a shading net. The trial also highlighted that the water use efficiency (WUE) of the SHS systems was not significantly better than traditional soil-based cultivation. This prompted the implementation of a more advanced system. A simplified Nutrient Film Technique (NFT) system was introduced on five private farms, each covering 12 m² (cultivable area) inside a greenhouse of 24 m² (3 x 8 m). Briefly, the system is composed of horizontal tubes slightly tilted (2%) to ensure the water recirculation. A pump continuously provides the nutrient solution which flows inside the tubes, where plants are transplanted. Any growing substrate is adopted here, and roots float in the nutrient solution. The irrigation followed a 45-minute watering and 15-minute drying cycle as recommended by the literature (Zolnier et al. 2004). This system incorporated an insect-proof net, a shading net on the roof, and an automated intermittent irrigation (Fig. 1). To test the system, romaine lettuce was grown, and the results demonstrated that both yield (kg m⁻²) and WUE (g FW L⁻¹) significantly outperformed the SHS plastic

bottle system (Fig. 2). Specifically, the WUE in the upgraded NFT system was 2.2 times higher than in soil-based cultivation.

Fig. 2 The upgraded system during crop growth (left) and one week before the harvest (right)

Fig. 3 Yield, surface needed per adult to satisfy the yearly lettuce requirements (set at 200 g day⁻¹), and water use efficiency of three growing systems (soil, simplified hydroponics with plastic bottles, and upgraded hydroponic system). Soil data were derived from Nagaz et al. 2013

Although the yield obtained in the upgraded system is lower, although still comparable, with that of on-soil cultivation, it allows a higher number of growing cycles along the year resulting in enhanced yearly production ($24.2 \text{ kg m}^{-2} \text{ year}^{-1}$ vs $16.8 \text{ kg m}^{-2} \text{ year}^{-1}$). While target farmers grow up to 2 growing cycles in a year (median value), the upgraded system can potentially allow for the cultivation of 8 growing cycles of 45 days each. However, our simulation for on-soil cultivation shown in Fig. 3 considered 4 growing cycles, which is the maximum value observed among target farmers. Non-stop lettuce production is, however, not sustainable in on-soil cultivation system, as soil health might be depleted because of the monoculture and absence of crop rotation. With the current productivity in upgraded hydroponic system in Northern Tunisia, 3 m^2 are sufficient to satisfy the yearly lettuce requirements of one adult, considering the hypothetical consumption of 200 g day^{-1} for a healthy diet. Consequently, the surface needed to satisfy the food requirements for an average adult is much lower for the upgraded system, implying a better land use efficiency (LUE) and avoid the environmental risk of monoculture. Furthermore, we calculated the efficiency of fertilizers used based on nitrogen (N) inputs used. In soil cultivation, an optimistic N rate is around 100 kg N ha^{-1} (although it is frequently much higher). In the upgraded simplified hydroponic system, 325 g of NPK fertilizers had been used (with 20% of N) on a surface of 12 m^2 , resulting in an equivalent rate of 54 kg N ha^{-1} . As in the upgraded system the yield was 3 kg m^{-2} , while in soil it can reach even 4.3 kg m^{-2} (Nagaz et al. 2013), the N use efficiency (NUE) was calculated as the ratio between the kg of N used and the yield obtained in one hectare (kg of produce obtained in one hectare from 1 kg of N supplied). From this analysis, the NUE in the upgraded system resulted $554 \text{ kg of lettuce kg}^{-1}$ of N, which is 29% higher than the NUE of the on-soil system ($430 \text{ kg kg}^{-1} \text{ N}$). We highlight that this analysis is based on assumption of N consumption and lettuce yield in on-soil cultivation system. For precaution, a lower N rate was assumed (it ranges typically from $100\text{-}150 \text{ kg N ha}^{-1}$).

A cost-benefit analysis (CBA) was conducted to evaluate operational costs and revenues under two irrigation scenarios: continuous irrigation ($24 \text{ hours day}^{-1}$) and intermittent irrigation ($12 \text{ hours day}^{-1}$ with 15-minute drying cycle per hour, and with nighttime irrigation pauses). The cost of pH and EC meters was depreciated over one year to determine the daily cost. The CBA clearly showed that energy costs for irrigation significantly impact total costs (Fig. 3). Indeed, under continuous irrigation, the system resulted in negative profit. However, with intermittent irrigation, as adopted by local farmers during validation trial, the profit margin became positive. With the average salary of farmers in Jendouba at approximately $\text{€}100$ per month (CEFA, personal communication), the adoption of

the upgraded hydroponic system with intermittent irrigation led to a 16% salary increase. Even with intermittent irrigation, energy costs still accounted for almost half of total operating costs (Fig. 4). Therefore, future research should focus on further optimizing irrigation efficiency. Reducing irrigation time from 45 to 30 minutes could potentially boost farmers' salary by 27% if productivity remains constant.

Table 2 Cost benefit analysis for upgraded hydroponic system under continuous and intermittent irrigation

			Continuous irrigation		Intermittent irrigation	
	Unit	€ unit ⁻¹	Use (n unit)	Cost	Use (n unit)	Cost
Magnesium sulphate	g	0.001	406	0.36	406	0.36
Calcium	g	0.003	292	0.73	292	0.73
NPK	g	0.0004	325	0.12	325	0.12
Phosphoric acid	mL	0.001	313	0.28	313	0.28
Electricity	kW	0.100	810	81.0	304	30.4
pH meter	daily use	0.236	48	11.3	48	11.3
EC meter	daily use	0.236	48	11.3	48	11.3
Plants	number	-	300	5	300	5
Other	-	-		5	-	5
Total				115.1		64.5
			Revenue		Revenue	
	Unit	Value				
Yield	kg m ⁻²	3.03				
Total production	kg	36.4				
Market price	€ kg ⁻¹	2.5	90.9		90.9	
Profit	per crop cycle		-24.2		26.4	
	per month		-15.1		16.5	

Fig. 4 Components of the total costs

Food Hub Akaki / Nifas Silk (ET)

Performance of romaine lettuce in hydroponics systems

The total number of lettuce plants grown in the simple standing hydroponics system (SSHS) was about 390 each having 11 to 15 healthy leaves at its harvesting stage (Table 3). The leaf area ranged from 117 to 223 cm². The readings on chlorophyll meter ranged from 18.5 to 21.82 which indicating to estimate total nitrogen content range 10.21 to 12.65 mg/dcm². The total biomass ranged from 4.58 to 6.29 kg and marketable product ranges from 2.70 to 4.47 kg.

Table 3. Performance of romaine lettuce in SSHS in Mekelle city, northern Ethiopia

Planting line	Leaf area (cm ²)	Leaves per plant	Chlorophyll reading	Total N content (mg/dcm ²)	Total biomass (kg)	Marketable product (kg)
1	117	11	18.15	10.21	4.58	2.70
2	119	11	18.88	10.69	4.85	3.02
3	162	12	19.26	10.94	5.03	3.19
4	143	13	19.84	11.33	5.25	3.32
5	120	13	20.09	11.50	5.31	3.37
6	172	13	20.39	11.70	5.41	3.59
7	196	14	20.77	11.95	5.49	3.61
8	223	14	21.03	12.13	5.82	3.89
9	226	14	21.77	12.61	5.94	4.04
10	228	15	21.82	12.65	6.29	4.47

Determining the plant population, leaf number per plant, leaf area for the lower, middle and upper leaves are found to be relevant to estimate the total leaf area

(Fig 5) in each planting line. The total N concentration can be estimated from readings of chlorophyll using the chlorophyll meter (Fig 5). The quantity of the marketable product can also predicted through measuring few plant samples (Fig 6).

Figure 5. Estimating total leaf area of lettuce in SSHS in Mekelle city, Ethiopia

Figure 6. Estimating total N content (mg/dcm²) of lettuce from measured chlorophyll concentration values in SSHS in Mekelle city, Ethiopia

Figure 6. Estimating total and marketable biomass of lettuce in SSHS in Mekelle city, Ethiopia

Water and nutrient saving efficiency

There were three four growing stages (periods) of the romaine lettuce. The lettuce plants use 150 litres of water during transplanting which about 42.86% of the total amount of water used by plants in the soil system (Fig. 7). The water consumed in the soil system is tripled at middle growing period and trend continued that way towards the maturity of the lettuce plants. The water use efficiencies can be calibrated using the functions as displayed in Figure 7 below.

Figure 7. Water saving efficiency of lettuce grown in SSHS of Mekelle city, Ethiopia

The prediction equations developed for estimating the cumulative water requirements (l), and of the soilless versus soil systems planted to romaine lettuce (Table 4 and figure 8). The water saving efficiency of the soilless system is predicted to range from 52 to 60% over 60 days, higher efficiency values recorded at early growth stages.

Table 4. Estimated decadal water use (l) of soilless and soil systems planted to romaine lettuce in Mekelle city, Ethiopia

Day	10	20	30	40	50	60	Equation: $y = ax^2 + bx + c$		
							A	b	C
Soils system	18.05	59.70	135.40	240.4	375.4	540.4	1.5	-2.3	4
Soilless system	10.50	35.65	75.80	130.95	201.1	286.25	0.75	-2.65	3.5
Water saving	10.19	32.47	80.46	147.76	235.30	343.10	0.75	0.35	0.05

Figure 8. Prediction equations developed for estimating the cumulative water requirements (l) of the soilless versus soil systems planted to romaine lettuce in Mekelle city, Ethiopia

The issues of land and water scarcity, pollution and environmental health are becoming forerunners in sustainable development programmes of rural and urban areas in most countries of the world. The shift from cereal-based food systems to safe and nutritious green leaf vegetable and fruit horticulture systems resulted in rethinking of existing gardening and horticulture systems. Thus, precision agriculture and vertical farming has been receiving attention. Simple hydroponics (SH) system in Ethiopia Mekelle city has proved to be more efficient

than the soil gardening systems, reducing water use by 60% during early growth stage to 50% as the growing period approaches to physiological maturity of romaine lettuce.

Studies showed that daily water requirement for soilless horticulture can even be very efficient in water consumption (2 l/m² vs 20 l/m²) for the traditional soil horticulture (Fecondini et al., 2010; Orsini et al., 2010a, b). Our results indicates the simple standing hydroponics system is found to be low input and suitable for small scale private gardening in dryland areas, in line with the conceptualizations of other workers (Caldeyro Stajano et al., 2003). The harvests per annum can be increased: for instance, 30 days versus 45 days in soil horticulture for lettuce; and 20–24 plants/m² versus 10–12 plants/m² for soil horticulture (Mezzetti et al., 2010). Labour costs in SH is also reduced (Orsini et al., 2010) making it appropriate for low-resource population to fulfil family food requirements and income.

2.2.2 Relevant production

Publications, conference abstracts / proceedings / posters, communication articles, news items, ...

Dissemination of experimental result of Tunisia Food Hub at the Italian Congress of Horticulture in Turin 2023 (poster presentation), and at V All Africa Horticultural Congress (AAHC2024) organized by International Society of Horticultural Science (ISHS) in Marrakech. Publication of experimental results as congress proceeding:

Cerasola, V.A., Jmayai, A., Viola, F., Jamai, D., Adamo, F., Costea, C., ... & Gianquinto, G. Simplified hydroponics in Tunisia: assessing the charred straw as growing substrate for lettuce cultivation. *In V All Africa Horticultural Congress (AAHC2024)*. In press.

Gebreyohannes Girmay, Simple hydroponics systems for peri-urban smallholder farmers in Ethiopia, 2025.

2.3 Summary of the outcomes

Number of food operators involved in the validation activities (WP5).

Food Hub	Innovation (new technology / system / tool / food product)	n. farmers / SMEs
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Jendouba (TN)	Upgraded simplified hydroponic systems	5
Jendouba (TN)	Community gardens	56
Akaki / Nifas Silk (ET)	Simple Standing Hydroponics System	120

2.4 Summary of the impacts

Key performance indicators (KPIs: technology, production, nutrition): measures

Food Hub	Innovation (new technology / system / tool / food product)	KPIs measuring the achievements
Jendouba, Tunisia	Upgraded simplified hydroponics	Increase of yearly productivity (+44%) as compared with on-soil cultivation
Jendouba, Tunisia	Upgraded simplified hydroponics	Soil use reduction (-25%) avoiding the risk of monoculture as compared with on-soil cultivation
Jendouba, Tunisia	Upgraded simplified hydroponics	Improvement of water use efficiency (WUE) by +218% as compared with on-soil cultivation, as well as increase of nitrogen use efficiency (NUE) by 29% as compared with on-soil cultivation
Jendouba, Tunisia	Upgraded simplified hydroponics	Positive Cost-Benefit Analysis, and increase of the average farmers' salary by 16%
Akaki / Nifas Silk (ET)	Simple Standing Hydroponics System	More nutrient dense vegetables (e.g. N content vs N) as compared with vegetables grown on soils
Akaki / Nifas Silk (ET)	Simple Standing Hydroponics System	Water saving (60% savings of the water)
Akaki / Nifas Silk (ET)	Simple Standing Hydroponics System	Private gardening expansion at backyards
Akaki / Nifas Silk (ET)	Simple Standing Hydroponics System	Request increasing for training (on preparation local substrates, local nutrient solution, and on skills of installation)
Akaki / Nifas Silk (ET)	Simple Standing Hydroponics System	Demand for system expansion by the adopter households for income generating purposes

3. Protocol for the implementation

This section adopts an operational perspective to describe how to implement and manage the prototype, thus ensuring its full functionality and usability. It includes the deployment requirements, procedures, methods, techniques, and practical considerations.

3.1 Framework conditions for the prototype

Scope of the prototype, including the general conditions for its implementation, its features, functionalities, and user interactions. This should also specify any limitations or constraints of the prototype.

Food Hub Jendouba (TN)

Upgraded simplified hydroponics. The upgraded simplified hydroponic system is designed to enhance the LUE and the WUE in regions where arable land and water resources are scarce. This system allows for year-round crop production while mitigating the environmental risks of monoculture. The hydroponic setup consists of several key components, including an insect-proof protective net, an automatic irrigation system, and a structural frame for plant cultivation (Fig. 1). Farmers managing this system require knowledge on nutrient solution preparation and management, including composition, monitoring, and adjustments. A technical training on these topics was provided by UNIBO and CEFA, using the information reported in the specific guidelines previously realized (D4.2). In this system, plants are transplanted into horizontal tubes with holes, where their roots float in a thin layer of circulating nutrient solution. The solution flows along the slight slope of the tubes, ensuring efficient drainage and recirculation. An automatic pump, activated at specific intervals, powers the water recirculation.

Farmers are responsible for defining the timing of solution circulation and pump operation, ensuring the roots are periodically drained to promote oxygenation. This is controlled by an actuator that allows precise timing regulation. Additionally, once or twice a week, farmers must monitor the nutrient solution using pH and EC meters, making adjustments with mineral fertilizers or acids as needed.

Despite the system's insect-proof net, phytosanitary monitoring is recommended once or twice a week to detect any potential diseases or pests. The system also includes a shading net, which can be adjusted based on external solar radiation to regulate internal light levels. The setup is particularly suited for compact crops such as lettuce, strawberries, and peppers, but it is less ideal for taller crops like tomatoes or cucumbers, which require more height for cultivation.

Community garden: the community garden aims to foster collaboration among local farmers by encouraging shared investment in climate-resilient technologies, such as drip irrigation systems. A total of 56 plots, each of 100 m², were implemented, with each plot equipped with a modular drip irrigation system. A well was dug in the area, and a photovoltaic-powered pump was installed to provide the necessary energy for irrigation.

A common warehouse was constructed to store shared materials, and participating farmers have access to a solar dryer (established through a different project component), enabling the production of innovative, value-added products such as spices and dried vegetables. Farmers can choose between different business models: they may grow vegetables for personal consumption or for sale in local markets, either as fresh produce or dried goods (Fig. 9).

Fig. 9 Business models for the community garden (left) and organization of responsibilities within the farmers community proposed (right)

Training sessions will be provided to farmers, focusing on two key areas. First, technical training will cover agroecological management techniques, including crop rotation, mulching, and drip irrigation, while mineral fertilization will integrate with the organic fertilization. Additionally, the public extension services (CRDA) will develop technical briefs for each specific crop—such as tomatoes, garlic, onions, and strawberries—providing tailored guidance to farmers.

Second, trainings will focus on administrative garden management using a bottom-up approach. Key management responsibilities will be identified (e.g., maintenance of materials, treasurer, logistics, and management of the solar dryer). Farmers will be selected to take on these roles, either voluntarily or through democratic elections. To ensure transparency and accountability, a farmers' assembly will be established. This assembly will hold regular meetings to monitor the performance of those in charge, address any management issues, and provide feedback for the continuous improvement of garden operations. To

ensure the correct working, the farmers will be supported during the initial meetings.

Finally, a set of regulations will be collaboratively developed by the farmers, outlining the rules and guidelines they will follow to ensure smooth and efficient management of the community garden.

Food Hub Akaki / Nifas Silk (ET)

Implementation protocol for the SSHS prototype involves a step wise approach

1. Select a specific site (3m by 6 m) for SSHS positioning in the private garden
2. Obtain PVC tubes (110mm diameter and 6m long), plastic T-tbas, plastic tea cups, substrate, small plastic water tanker, watering can, measuring cylinder
3. Seal both ends of the PVCs with the T-tabs and then prepare small diameter holes on the PVCs,
4. Prepare the plastic tea cups by making small tear at its base and sides
5. Obtain 6 main and 20 minor wooden poles (e.g., Eucaliptus common in Ethiopia) to prepare levelled support stand for carrying the tubes
6. Fill in the plastic tea cups with the substrate and get ready for transplanting
7. Prepare clean water, nutrient solution to fill into the PVCs
8. Obtain healthy seedlings of the selected vegetable crop
9. Do planting during late afternoon
10. Prepare monitoring plans, and water & nutrient replacement schedule
11. Follow up regularly

3.2 Prerequisites for the prototype / Technical architecture

Technical components and infrastructure necessary to build the prototype, including equipment, inputs and raw materials, personnel, costs, ...

Food Hub Jendouba (TN)

The primary prerequisite for the upgraded hydroponics system is a reliable electricity supply, which is essential for the automatic circulation of the nutrient solution. To protect the system's electric components, particularly the pump's electric actuator, a plastic roof is highly recommended. Alternatively, waterproof

boxes can be used to shield the actuator, enabling the system to function completely outdoors.

In the Tunisian climate, a shading net is advisable to prevent heat stress during the summer months. Although an insect-proof net can be included, it is not strictly necessary. Omitting the insect-proof net eliminates the need for a supporting iron frame, which significantly reduces investment costs. However, a sturdy frame (iron or plastic fixed in the soil) is required to support the plastic channels in which the plants will grow.

From a management perspective, EC (electrical conductivity) and pH meters are necessary to monitor and adjust the nutrient solution. Essential inputs for the nutrient solution include NPK fertilizers with microelements, calcium, magnesium, and phosphoric acid for pH control.

Ref.	Requirement description	Priority*
1	Insect-proof net	3
2	Removable shading net	1
3	Plastic roof cover	1
4	Pump	M
5	Actuator for automatic irrigation	M
6	Plastic poles for plant cultivation	M
7	Iron frame to support plastic poles	M
8	Mineral fertilizers and acid	M
9	Electricity	M
10	EC and pH meter	M
* Priority: M = mandatory / 1 = high, 2 = medium, 3 = low		

Food Hub Akaki / Nifas Silk (ET)

The simple hydroponics system (SHS) is easy and non-labour intensive. The simplicity of our SSHS prototype can step-by-step be innovatively transformed into an intermediate and high-tech levels which basically ensures sustainability.

Ref.	Requirement description	Priority*
1	Architecture designing costs	3

2	Installation (Tools, materials and instruments) cost	1
3	Personnel (skill)	1
4	Seeds and seedling costs	1
5	Water and nutrient management costs	1
6	Plant maintenance and management	2
* Priority: M = mandatory / 1 = high, 2 = medium, 3 = low		

3.3 Implementation plan

This section outlines the implementation process, including indicative timeline, milestones, and any specific task associated with the innovation adoption.

Food Hub Jendouba (TN)

Upgraded hydroponic system (UHS)

The steps for the implementation of the UHS are here resumed:

1. Design of the system: the UHS system was designed according to the farmers requirements, and the materials needed were quantified and purchased.
2. Soil levelling: a flat area was chosen (the flatter the better), and it was levelized as much as possible. In this stage a hole was realized where the future tank for the irrigation will be placed. Then the soil was covered with a plastic sheet to improve the walkability inside the future greenhouse
3. Iron frame installation: the iron frame that supports the greenhouse (e.g., the insect-proof net, the roof plastic cover, and the shading net) was fixed to the soil
4. Covering with plastic sheet and with the shading net
5. Installation of the iron frame supporting the channels for plants' cultivation
6. Installation of the irrigation and drainage system and placement of the channels for cultivation
7. Covering with the perimetral insect-proof net
8. Installation of the electric actuator of the pump
9. Test of the system and transplant

STEP	Days													
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	
System design and material purchase	█													
Soil levelling											█			
Iron frame installation											█			
Plastic and shading net roof											█			
Iron frame for cultivation												█		
Irrigation and drainage installation												█		
Insect-proof net													█	
Electric actuator													█	
Test and transplant													█	

Figure 10 Hypothetical Gantt chart for the implementation of the upgraded hydroponic system

Food Hub Akaki / Nifas Silk (ET)

The implementation process (taking lettuce into account) includes

1. *Initial stage*: starts with the initial installation of SSHS which involves selecting site, constructing support structure, positioning the plant growing medium and substrate and planting. This would take 7 days when all tools and materials are made accessible
2. *Seedling establishment stage*: refers to the first 10 days after planting where intensive follow up is required seeing the plant roots are growing into the nutrient solution. It may require beating-up of damaged or mal performing seedlings.
3. *Early growth stage*: refers to a period from growing many new leaves after the plant leaves that were there during transplanting disappears. At the stage the roots of the green-leaf vegetables are growing fast displaying white color indicating to a healthy performance. This can be seen 10-20 day after transplanting. Monitoring the pH and EC of the nutrient solution is important and is the right time to improve the nutrient concentration through replenishing with new additional nutrients from the reservoir.
4. *Maturity stage*: refers to a period where increasing root length and density in the solution as well as in the substrate are observed. The plant also produces stem-like part indicating to increasing plant height and leaf numbers during the 20-40 days after transplanting period. Monitoring the pH and EC of the nutrient solution is important and increased amounts of water and nutrients are important. At this demonstration can be done to create linkage to support services such as markets, funding organizations, new adopters interest groups, etc.

5. *Completing the cycle for next planting:* based on the feed backs of visitors, markets, consumers, new plans can be prepared for repeating the process. At the stage the sustainability indicators can start to emerge and it always important to take records of major success/damage events to build the system better.

3.4 Management

This section outlines any specific aspect or task associated with the management, control, evaluation and maintenance of the implemented innovation.

Upgraded hydroponics: the management of the UHS requires little knowledge on the nutrient solution (quantity of fertilizers to be supplied) along the year, as well as the timing of irrigation. The farmer should adjust the EC and the irrigation timing as a function of the external temperatures. During warm periods, the water uptake is generally higher, therefore a reduced EC must be ensured to avoid phytotoxic effect to plants due to excessive uptake of nutrients. In this regard, also irrigation must be readapted: while during fall and winter seasons longer drying cycle of the irrigation can be adopted (which is essential also to ensure the profitability of the system), in spring and summer this should be reduced. A training was provided to farmers in-situ from UNIBO team both for nutrient and irrigation management. The specific information on nutrient management have been already included in the technical guidelines (D4.2) translated in Arabic, while future readaptation will include information on the irrigation management too.

Furthermore, knowledge on the management of the lighting inside the greenhouse is also required, as the shading net should be used only during the warmer periods (summer season). A quick indication can be found in Table 5.

Table 5 Indicative electrical conductivity (EC) of the nutrient solution and the indication on the use of the shading net according the external temperature of intervention area of Fernena

	Min-max temperature (°C)	Shading net	EC
January	3 – 14	no	2000-2500 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$
February	4 – 15	no	2000-2500 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$
March	5 – 18	no	2000-2500 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$
April	7 – 21	no	2000-2500 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$
May	11 – 27	no	1800-2000 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$
June	15 – 32	yes/no	1500-1700 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$
July	18 – 36	yes	1200-1500 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$
August	19 – 35	yes	1200-1500 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$
September	16 – 31	yes/no	1500-1700 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$
October	12 – 26	no	1800-2000 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$

November	8 – 19	no	2000-2500 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$
December	4 – 16	no	2000-2500 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$

Community garden: the technical management of the community garden will be guided by the technical assistance provided by the public extension services (CRDA), which aims at transferring the technical knowledge to handle with drip irrigation, mulching, and crop rotation.

4. Conclusions

Final considerations and evaluations including recommendations, possible implications (organizational, operational, policy, ...) and technological improvements, R&I needs and way forward.

Food Hub Jendouba (TN)

The upgraded hydroponics system has proven to be effective in optimizing water use (+218%) and nitrogen fertilizer efficiency (+29%) compared to traditional on-soil cultivation. However, a significant drawback is the high energy cost associated with irrigation, making it crucial to select an appropriate irrigation strategy to ensure the system's economic sustainability. Intermittent irrigation has emerged as a valuable solution, dramatically reducing energy consumption and enhancing profitability. When this method is employed, the average farmer's salary can increase by 16%. It is important to test this approach across different seasons, as the length of the growing cycle varies with external temperatures, affecting overall energy consumption. Further research is needed to identify the optimal irrigation strategy, focusing on the most economically efficient balance between drying and irrigation cycles throughout the year. For instance, reducing the irrigation duration from the current 45 minutes to 30 minutes could potentially increase average salaries from the actual +16% to +27%, assuming that crop yields remain stable. Moreover, the hydroponic system requires less surface area to meet the lettuce consumption needs of an average adult compared to on-soil cultivation, while also mitigating the risks associated with lettuce monoculture, which can lead to the spread of fungal diseases. On the other hand, the community garden is anticipated to deliver social and economic benefits to farmers. Beyond technical training, establishing a solid organizational framework and fostering a cohesive community is vital for the long-term success of the garden area. To this end, it is essential to appoint responsible individuals for various thematic areas (such as dryer management, materials procurement, and maintenance), allowing farmers to self-organize under the guidance and support of CEFA. This approach aims to establish a robust community through a bottom-up methodology.

Food Hub Akaki / Nifas Silk (ET)

The simple hydroponics systems are trending precision vertical farming agriculture which is becoming routine in urban and peri-urban areas. Our SSHS experience indicates that this technological innovation can relieve the healthy diet requirements and food security of poor people. This is pro-poor technological innovation and can be suitable for stressed environments and drylands. It is also a new form of conservation-based modern agriculture system which indicates to its suitability once it is integrated national systems. Therefore, some policy briefs and platforms for SHS are very important for this technological innovation will be scaled out to the general public.

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